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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF BIODIESEL AND RENEWABLE DIESEL AS MOTOR FUELS

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to consider and compare fuel properties of biodiesel and renewable diesel as alternative to petroleum diesel. Though produced from similar feedstock, they are fundamentally different types of biofuels. Biodiesel represents fatty acid methyl esters produced by transesterification, in the course of which organic fats and oils are converted into fatty acid alkyl esters by reacting with alcohols and catalysts. Biodiesel contains oxygen, which makes it chemically different from the regular ultra-low sulphur diesel. Renewable diesel is a paraffinic biomass-based liquid fuel originating from many types of vegetable oils as well as animal fats. Hydrotreating is the most common process to obtain hydrotreated vegetable oil, which is renewable biodiesel. Hydrotreated vegetable oil is a hydrocarbon fuel that is considered a “drop-in” replacement for petroleum diesel. Wide introduction of biofuels in the transport sector is an important part of the global green transition and climate change mitigation. Similar to bioethanol for petrol engines, biodiesel and renewable diesel are the alternative to fossil fuel use in diesel engines. The choice between biodiesel and renewable diesel or even other biofuels suitable for the diesel engine depends on a number of technical, environmental and economic factors.

Keywords: biomass, biofuels, biodiesel, fatty acid methyl ester, hydrotreated vegetable oil.

Introduction.

The transport sector represents more than 30% of the total final energy consumption (TFEC) in the world. The biggest part of energy in transport, which is equivalent to more than 2.1 Gtoe/y in 2022 (77% of the total) is consumed by the road transport. At that aviation accounts only for about 8% of TFEC in the transport sector and marine transport accounts for 10%, the rest being rail transport and pipeline transfer. Globally, transport remains the sector with the lowest share of renewables in TFEC, which is about 4% (2021). For comparison: the consumption of renewable energy (RE) is nearly 17% in industry and 16% in buildings; renewables cover 10% of the global heat consumption and 30% of electricity consumption. Of the renewables in transport, biofuels account for 3.5%, the rest being renewable electricity. By the subsectors, rail transport uses 15% of renewable energy, road transport uses about 5%, while the share of RE in aviation and marine transport is negligible. These facts emphasize the necessity to increase global efforts on RE uptake in the transport sector to reduce the consumption of fossil

fuels and therefore decrease the emission of greenhouse gases (GHG).

The article considers biofuels for the road transport, as this subsector is the most energy-consuming with comparatively low current share of renewables and quite big potential for improvement. The global production of biofuels is continuously rising, having achieved about 175 billion litres per year by now. Since 2005, the production has increased nearly by six times, starting at the beginning of the period with sugarcane and corn ethanol as well as biodiesel (I-generation biofuels), and gradually adding cellulosic biofuels and other advanced fuels (Figure 1). Technologies for the production of II-generation (advanced) biofuels give the opportunity to obtain ethanol, dimethylfuran, dimethyl ether, Fischer-Tropsch diesel, and mixed alcohols (Lalman 2016). The advanced biofuels are often not cost competitive with I-generation biofuels; however, they have a huge potential for GHG emission reduction, which is their undisputable advantage.

Figure 1. Global production of biofuels, Ml.

In particular, the article focuses on biomass-based diesel, which can be distinguished as Fatty Acid Methyl Ester (FAME) and Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil (HVO). In literature, especially in statistics, the term “bio-diesel” is sometimes used meaning FAME along with HVO. However, it is important to note that FAME and HVO are fundamentally different types of biofuels, which will be considered below. Currently, fatty acid

methyl ester is the type of biomass-based diesel that is mostly produced and used in the world (Figure 2). The production of hydrotreated vegetable oil started after 2010 and has been gradually increasing since then. HVO can be also referred to as renewable diesel or green diesel.

Figure 2. Global consumption of selected biofuels, Mtoe.

Methodology.

Different nature of FAME and renewable diesel is caused by technologies by which they are produced. This determines their fuel properties and differences between each other and the traditional diesel. Typical feedstock for FAME (biodiesel) production is vegetable oils or animal fats (bio-lipids). FAME is produced by transesterification, in the course of which organic fats and oils are converted into fatty acid alkyl esters by reacting with alcohols and catalysts. In fact, the transesterification process is the chemical breaking of fatty

acids contained in vegetable oils using alcohol to form alcohol esters and glycerol, aiming to lower the viscosity and volatility of vegetable oil (Bezergianni 2013). Typically, methanol is applied as the reactant and creates fatty acid methyl esters. One of the reasons for using fatty acid methyl esters in biodiesel production, rather than free fatty acids, is to mitigate the potential corrosion they can cause to engines, production facilities, and related infrastructure. Biodiesel contains oxygen, which makes it chemically different from the regular ultra-low sulphur diesel (diesel EN 590).

Renewable diesel is a paraffinic biomass-based liquid fuel originating from many types of vegetable oils as well as animal fats (Dimitriadis 2018). HVO can be obtained via several production processes. In the USA, the most common process is hydroprocessing (hydrotreating) (Gerweni 2023). Hydrotreating parallels cracking crude oil into gasoline, diesel, and other petroleum products in a crude oil refinery. As a result, HVO production facilities are increasingly converted parts of crude oil refineries or the parts that complete conversions of refineries. However, some installations are entirely new refinery facilities. Based on the existing economic conditions, each facility has the potential to switch between crude oil, organic fats and oils refining. The investment costs are much higher for renewable diesel versus FAME production, since crude oil refining technology is used to obtain HVO. Renewable diesel is fundamentally different from FAME as it contains only hydrogen and carbon. So, HVO is a hydrocarbon fuel that is considered a “drop-in” replacement for petroleum diesel. That means that it does not require blending with petroleum diesel for the application in modern diesel engines as a fuel that meets specifications. The drop-in nature of HVO is its considerable advantage over FAME.

Main part.

The diesel engine named after its inventor, Rudolph Diesel, is an internal combustion engine that runs on diesel fuel (light petroleum fuel). The diesel engine is a gasoline-type piston engine, but only air (not the fuel-air mixture) enters the cylinder during the first stroke of the piston. The piston rises and compresses the air to a very high temperature. At this moment, the pump injects fuel, and due to the high temperature of the air, it ignites. While the fuel is burning, the piston goes down, which is a working stroke. Diesel engines are commonly used by trucks, buses, and trains. They are also used in tractors and harvesters as well as in various industrial and marine applications such as power generators, pumps and compressors.

Similar to gasoline (petrol), diesel fuel is another commonly used motor fuel, but it is more typical for heavy trucks and buses. Diesel fuel is a middle distillate stream in refineries, with a boiling point ranging 160 to 380 °C (Betiha 2018). There are different types of diesel fuels authorised for the use in the diesel engine: petroleum diesel (DERV, red diesel); paraffinic diesel (HVO, GTL fuel); FAME (biodiesel). Main properties of these fuels are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1.

Fuel properties of fuels suitable for diesel engines.

Parameter	Diesel EN 590	GTL fuel	FAME (bi-diesel)	HVO (UOP Ecofining™)	HVO (Neste Oil)
Oxygen content, %	not specified	0	11	0	0
Density at 15 °C, kg/l	0.820-0.845	760-783	0.883	0.780	0.775-0.785
Viscosity at 40 °C, mm ² /s	2-3.5	2.3-2.7	4.5	~3.5	~3.5
Cetane number	>51	70-89	>56	70-90	75-99
Sulphur content, mg/kg	<10	<1	<10	<2	0
Lower heating value, MJ/kg	not specified (typically, 43.1)	43.7-44	37.1	44	44
Aromatic hydrocarbons content, % vol.	<11	~0	0	0	0

Diesel Engine Road Vehicle (DERV), also referred to as white diesel, ultra-low sulphur diesel (diesel EN 590) and road diesel, is most commonly used as fuel for vehicles with diesel engines. Red diesel is applied in the construction and farming industries, mainly in machinery and off-road vehicles. Its chemical composition is the same as regular automobile fuel; however, red diesel has a high sulphur content, which makes it suitable for off-road use. Gas-to-liquids (GTL) fuel is an alternative to conventional diesel. GTL fuel is derived from natural gas and has better emissions characteristics than petroleum diesel. In particular, GTL fuel has lower emissions of particulate matter, sulphur oxides, and nitrogen oxides (Ismael 2024).

FAME (biodiesel) has some fuel properties that are better than those of mineral diesel. First, the emission of a number of harmful substances is much lower. In comparison with petroleum diesel combustion, the emission reduction is 56% for hydrocarbons, 55% for solid particles, 43% for carbon oxides, 5-10% for nitrogen oxides, and 60% for soot (Riabtsev 2014). When

burning biodiesel, the exhaust gases are white, and not black in contrast with diesel. Other FAME's advantages include better lubricating properties, higher ignition temperature, higher cetane number. In case of getting into the soil or water, biodiesel does not harm the environment, because it is processed by microorganisms within 21 days by 90% and within 28 days by 99% (Dygun 2015).

It is considered that biodiesel can be used in its pure form (B100) or mixed in any proportion with diesel (B5, B10, B50, etc.), though the question has not been completely studied and settled yet. Most diesel engine manufacturers support only diesel blends up to B20, with higher blends requiring fuel system modifications. According to Peugeot and Citroen standards, diesel engines can run on B30. Scania and Volkswagen have different regulations that allow 100% biodiesel for most of their engines (Dygun 2015).

Biodiesel as fuel has some disadvantages that a user should be aware of. The freezing point of biodiesel is several degrees higher than that of diesel.

Therefore, at low temperatures, it is necessary to add appropriate additives or mix biodiesel with "winter" diesel in 50:50 proportions. Biodiesel may erode natural rubbers and some elastomers. To avoid the damage, it is necessary to replace parts made of such materials with those that are not affected by biodiesel or use biodiesel mixtures B5-B30. Since the mid-1990s, European and American engine manufacturers have not used biodiesel-sensitive materials in their products. FAME, as a good solvent, can wash away all the dirt that was collected in the fuel tank and pipelines before. It is necessary to periodically monitor the condition of fuel filters during first months of using biodiesel. As FAME is hydrophilic, a contamination with water could lead to microbiological contaminations of the fuel, filter clogging or tank corrosion. However, these disadvantages can be minimized by blending biodiesel with fossil diesel and using modern engine systems (Neuling 2019).

HVO is produced by hydrotreating vegetable oils, which guarantees obtaining high-quality fuel, the chemical structure of which is almost identical to the petroleum diesel. The quality of feedstock for HVO production can be equivalent or even much lower than that used for the production of conventional biodiesel (FAME). However, the finished product is much superior in its properties to biodiesel. HVO can be characterized as a stable, environmentally friendly and high-quality fuel with better combustion characteristics, filtration capacity, and engine operation at low temperatures. HVO is an alternative to conventional diesel fuel. This means that almost any engine, piece of equipment, and vehicle can be easily switched from diesel to HVO.

Renewable diesel has a lower density and significantly higher energy content as compared to biodiesel. These effects are mainly connected with the complete removal of oxygen, which results in a lower specific mass while the energy content increases. Another difference is caused by the absence of ester groups and unsaturated double bonds in hydrotreated vegetable Oil. In addition, the cetane number and therefore the ignitability of HVO is much better than that of FAME or petroleum diesel (see Table 1) as the amount of unbranched linear alkanes is high enough in renewable diesel. The boiling range of biodiesel is approximately 100 °C higher than that of fossil diesel, while HVO boils in a similar range as conventional diesel. This fact favours to achieve an optimal fuel combustion in modern engines and to avoid FAME related problems, such as the enrichment of FAME in the engine oil.

Different variations of renewable diesel consist primarily of paraffinic hydrocarbons and include no aromatic compounds, oxygen and sulphur. They show better stability than biodiesel and higher energy density on a mass basis as compared to petroleum diesel. Despite some authors' results that HVO has better low-temperature properties than other biofuels, they are still worse in comparison with conventional diesel (Pechout 2019).

Findings.

Wide introduction of biofuels in the transport sector is an important part of the global green transition and climate change mitigation. Similar to bioethanol for petrol engines, biodiesel and renewable diesel are the alternative to fossil fuel use in diesel engines. The choice between FAME and HVO or other biofuels (for example, GTL fuel) depends on a number of technical, environmental and economic factors.

As regards GHG emissions, FAME (from vegetable oils) and HVO are similar. According to Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (RED III), the typical value of GHG emission saving is 52-57% for biodiesel (from rapeseed, sunflower, soybean) and 51-58% for HVO (from rapeseed, sunflower, soybean) as compared to fossil biodiesel. Biofuels from waste have much higher GHG emission savings: 88% and 84% for biodiesel from waste cooking oil and animal fats from rendering, respectively; 87% and 83% for hydrotreated oil from waste cooking oil and animal fats from rendering, respectively. These values are important when it is obligatory to meet RED III sustainability criteria in terms of GHG emission reduction: at least 65 % for biofuels, biogas consumed in the transport sector, and bioliquids produced in installations starting operation from 1 January 2021. Historically, the biodiesel market has dominated in the EU, where the majority of vehicles run on diesel, unlike the situation in other parts of the world.

Having better fuel properties than FAME, HVO is notably more expensive (Figure 3). Analysis of structure of the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) shows that feedstock cost accounts for nearly 95% of FAME LCOE. As for HVO, its LCOE is determined mostly by hydrogen cost. If hydrogen is obtained by glycerol steam reforming (GSR), the share of hydrogen cost in LCOE structure may come to about 50%, the second biggest share (>30%) being the feedstock cost (see Figure 3) (Mustika 2021).

Figure 3. Structure of LCOE of FAME and HVO, USD/l.

In Europe, HVO is 25-55% as expensive as biodiesel from rapeseed. The upper bound corresponds to HVO from recycled vegetable oils (used cooking oil, palm oil mill effluent), providing GHG emission reduction of 85% min (class II) (Table 2). The use of waste oils as feedstock allows to avoid the competition with food crops and promotes waste recycling. The current production of waste vegetable oils is assessed as 700-1000 kt/y in Europe. The main challenges associated with the use of these resources are their collection and treatment (Lorenzi 2020).

For Ukraine's conditions, the production of FAME as well as HVO can be suitable and feasible depending on the field of application and production scale. According to the current diesel fuel standard DSTU 7688, the sale of fuel with a FAME content of up to 7% by volume is permitted. For a higher content

of biodiesel, other standards are applied, and it is necessary to inform the consumer about FAME content with an appropriate label at the filling station, for example, B10, B20, B100. One of possible areas of use higher FAME blends is agricultural machinery. Tractors running on diesel could even switch to pure biodiesel that is produced at small- and medium-scale plants in rural areas. An important aspect of this approach is that the produced biodiesel should be of high quality, so that not to negatively affect the tractor engine. Unfortunately, in early 2000s, Ukraine had some negative experience of using low-quality biodiesel in tractors. Another concept may be the production of HVO at the existing crude oil refineries. The obtained HVO will replace petroleum diesel in the road transport, which is very important for attaining the national target on renewable energy in the transport sector.

Table 2.

Biofuel prices comparison in 2020-2022, USD/t.

Type of biofuel, world region	2020	2021	2022
Biodiesel:			
from rapeseed (Europe)	963	1737	1969
from soybean (Argentina)	810	1254	1456
from palm oil (Indonesia)	710	1093	1335
HVO			
North-West Europe, class I ¹⁾	1337	1962	2493
North-West Europe, class II ²⁾	1779	2342	3078
North-West Europe, class III ³⁾	1668	2156	2751
Bioethanol:			
North-West Europe	877	1080	1472
USA	457	811	804
Brazil	668	1054	1128
China	928	1122	1159

1. HVO from food crops, providing GHG emission reduction of 65% min (class I).

2. HVO from recycled vegetable oils (used cooking oil, palm oil mill effluent), providing GHG emission reduction of 85% min (class II).

3. HVO from category 3 animal fats, providing GHG emission reduction of 80% min (class III).

According to Ukraine's National Energy and Climate Plan until 2030, the share of RE in the gross final energy consumption (GFEC) in transport should reach 14% in 2030. The national indicative target for RE in GFEC in transport set by the National Renewable Energy Action Plan is even higher – 17.2% in 2030. In any

case, to attain the aim, Ukraine should activate the uptake of biofuels, in particular FAME and HVO, in its transport sector.

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